

FREQUENCY AND CAUSES OF READMISSION WITHIN 30 DAYS OF DISCHARGE IN PATIENTS UNDERGOING PRIMARY PERCUTANEOUS CORONARY INTERVENTION

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Abstract

Objective:

To determine the frequency and causes of 30 days readmission in patient undergoing Primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PPCI).

Methods:

This descriptive study including 150 patients of acute myocardial infarction (AMI) who were planned for PPCI was conducted in a tertiary care cardiac facility in Pakistan. Readmission rate within 30 days of discharge from the hospital was noted. Causes of readmission such as STEMI, NSTEMI, stent thrombosis, heart failure, ventricular tachycardia, atrial fibrillation and conduction disorders were noted.

Results:

The baseline characteristics of the patient cohort were as follows: The mean age was 53.98 years with a standard deviation of 6.65 years. Among the participants, 68.7% (103 individuals) were male and 31.3% (47 individuals) were female. Among the 150 patients, 15 (10.0%) were readmitted within 30 days following PPCI. The frequencies of factors contributing to readmission were as follows: ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) occurred in 2 patients (1.3%), non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) in 3 patients (2.0%), and stent thrombosis in 2 patients (1.3%). Heart failure was observed in 6 patients (4.0%), and ventricular tachycardia was reported in 2 (1.3%) patients.

Conclusion:

In our study, the 30-day hospital readmission rate after discharge for patients undergoing primary percutaneous intervention was 10.0%. Common causes included heart failure, NSTEMI, and STEMI.

INTRODUCTION:

Cardiovascular diseases, such as myocardial infarction (MI) and heart failure, continue to be the primary cause of mortality in developed nations. Their prevalence is rising in low- and middle-income countries, driven by increasing common risk factors like smoking and obesity.¹ The primary goal in the acute management of ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) is to

restore blood flow to the heart muscle through the reopening of the blocked artery. Prompt reperfusion therapy is linked to improved patient outcomes.² Treatment options include thrombolytic agents and primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI). Numerous randomized controlled trials and scholarly meta-analyses have demonstrated that primary PCI offers better survival rates, lowers the risk of

reinfarction, and is generally more effective than thrombolytic therapy for STEMI patients.³

Percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) remains the most frequently performed revascularization procedure for patients with coronary artery disease in the United States. Advances in stent design, pharmacological treatments, and interventional techniques have led to improved procedural results over the years, with notably lower rates of in-hospital mortality and complications.^{4,5}

Unplanned readmissions after primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) are significant because they impose a burden on patients and healthcare services.⁶ Readmissions can result from actions taken or missed during the initial hospital stay, and their rates are viewed as indicators of quality of care. Inadequate treatment and poor coordination of services at discharge and during ongoing care may lead to readmissions.⁷ Unplanned rehospitalizations are generally seen as negative outcomes for patients and may be linked to complications from the PCI procedure itself or in-hospital management.⁸

The aim of present study was to determine the frequency and factors leading to readmission of patients within 30 days after PPCI.

METHODS:

In this descriptive case series, we included 150 patients who underwent primary PCI in a

tertiary care hospital in Pakistan. We only included patients with AMI and aged up to 70 years. While we excluded patients who presented with non-STEMI, those who had previously undergone coronary artery bypass grafting, or those who had undergone previous PCI were excluded.

Data of all PCI patients were entered prospectively at the time of the PCI by the operator and catheterization laboratory staff. Demographic information like age, gender and residential address was obtained. Data through hospital discharge were captured by nurses.

The data was analyzed by using SPSS Version 23. Quantitative variables were presented as mean ± standard deviation. Qualitative variables including readmission within 30 days and causes of 30 days readmission were presented in form of frequency and percentage.

RESULTS:

The baseline characteristics of the patient cohort were as follows: The mean age was 53.98 years with a standard deviation of 6.65 years. Among the participants, 68.7% (103 individuals) were male and 31.3% (47 individuals) were female. In terms of comorbidities, 45.3% (68 patients) had diabetes and 70.7% (106 patients) had hypertension. Furthermore, 44.0% (66 patients) were identified as smokers (Table 1).

Table 1. Baseline Patient’s Characteristics.

Age	53.98±6.65
Gender (%)	
Male	103 (68.7%)
Female	47 (31.3%)
Diabetes	68 (45.3%)
Hypertension	106 (70.7%)
Smoking	66 (44.0%)

Figure 1. Frequency of Readmission.

Among the 150 patients, 15 (10.0%) were readmitted within 30 days following PPCI (Figure 1).

The frequencies of factors contributing to readmission were as follows: ST-elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI) occurred in 2

patients (1.3%), non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction (NSTEMI) in 3 patients (2.0%), and stent thrombosis in 2 patients (1.3%). Heart failure was observed in 6 patients (4.0%), and ventricular tachycardia was reported in 2 (1.3%) patients (Table 2).

Table 2. Frequency of Factors Leading to Readmission.

STEMI	2 (1.3%)
NSTEMI	3 (2.0%)
Stent Thrombosis	2 (1.3%)
Heart Failure	6 (4.0%)
Ventricular Tachycardia	2 (1.3%)

DISCUSSION:

Survival rates among patients with acute myocardial infarction (AMI) have improved substantially over time.⁹ This improvement is primarily attributed to the implementation of early revascularization techniques, which have been validated by randomized controlled trials demonstrating that prompt revascularization improves both immediate and long-term survival outcomes.¹⁰

The 30-day readmission rate following the initial hospital stay has been employed as a measure of healthcare quality during adult hospitalizations.¹¹ In our study, readmission rate within 30 days after PPCI was 10.0%.

Shah and colleagues documented a 20.2% rate of hospital readmission within 30 days among patients who survived their initial hospitalization for acute myocardial infarction-related cardiogenic shock (AMI-CS) during the years 2013 and 2014, using data from the Nationwide Readmissions Database (NRD).¹⁰ Similarly, Mahmoud and team reported an 18.6% 30-day readmission rate for AMI-CS

patients, also utilizing the NRD.¹² In another investigation, Shah et al. identified a 22.6% rate of readmission within 30 days for survivors of cardiogenic shock not caused by myocardial infarction, again using NRD data.¹³ However, these previous studies did not specify 30-day readmission rates for patients who underwent PPCI during their initial hospital stay.^{12,13}

Hannan et al. analyzed 30-day readmissions in the 2007 New York State PCI registry, involving 40,093 patients. They found a 15.6% readmission rate, with 20.5% of these patients undergoing staged procedures. Excluding staged cases, the rate was 12.4%. Patients treated for acute myocardial infarction had higher readmission rates (17.3%) compared to elective cases (15.4%). Among readmitted patients without staged PCI, 58% had cardiac causes. Key predictors included age over 65, female sex, low ejection fraction, triple vessel disease, and comorbidities like peripheral vascular disease, COPD, diabetes, and renal failure. Longer hospital stays also increased readmission risk.¹⁴

Khawaja et al. analyzed 30-day readmissions after PCI in 15,498 cases from 1998 to 2008 in Rochester, USA. The overall readmission rate was 9.4%, highest for emergency (13.8%) and urgent (10.8%) procedures, lowest for elective (8.0%). Over two-thirds of readmitted patients had cardiac causes, though not specified. Readmission within 30 days was linked to significantly higher one-year mortality.¹⁵

The GHOST Registry studied early readmissions after PCI at a rural center from 2001-2009 with 5,706 patients—1.7% in-hospital mortality. Early readmission occurred in 11.4%, mostly for cardiac issues like angina, MI, revascularization, and heart failure. Non-cardiac readmissions lacked definition. Unlike other studies, MI diagnosis at PCI did not increase readmission risk (45% vs 42%), also true for NSTEMI (24% vs 22%) and STEMI (21% vs 20%). Non-elective cases predicted readmission (72% vs 62%). Patients readmitted within 30 days had higher one-year mortality (aHR 2.2; CI 1.4–3.4) and major adverse cardiovascular events, also with increased risk 1.8–2.8).¹⁶

A lack of early follow-up has been linked to a higher risk of readmission among patients with AMI and may also influence PCI patients. Early follow-up helps patients and clinicians ensure understanding, compliance, and assess the effectiveness of treatments. The educational aspect of follow-up is crucial because, in one study, fewer than half of the patients could identify their diagnoses, medications, their purposes, and possible side effects at discharge. Education provided at discharge and during early follow-up should also be tailored to the patient's education level, which has previously been associated with the risk of readmission among Medicare beneficiaries.

CONCLUSION:

In our study, the 30-day hospital readmission rate after discharge for patients undergoing primary percutaneous intervention was 10.0%. Common causes included heart failure, NSTEMI, and STEMI.

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